

PECULIARITIES OF METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation Social changes that have occurred in our republic in recent years have significantly changed the requirements for graduates of general secondary education. For a graduate today, it means that not only having certain knowledge, but also the formation of skills should be considered as the most important factor.

Key words: factor, economic, specialized subjects, future teacher.

There are four main blocks in the methodical training of undergraduate students of "Mathematics Teaching Methodology": humanitarian and socio-economic; mathematics and natural science; includes thorough education in general professional subjects and specialized subjects. The basic academic subjects that are formed as a mathematics teacher are included in the block of specialized subjects, and the subject of mathematics teaching methodology is included in the block of general professional subjects.

Personnel training The national program of personnel training is aimed at the radical reform of the continuous education and training process, in which higher education occupies a special place. One of the important tasks of higher education institutions is to provide high-level target education and training of qualified personnel on the basis of modern educational programs. Fulfilling such requirements of reform of higher education, first of all, places great responsibility on the teacher.

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President Sh. Mirziyoyev of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan In his celebratory speech dedicated to the 24th anniversary, he emphasized the following words about young people: "Currently, youth education remains an issue that will never lose its relevance and importance for us. Today's fast-changing world is opening new opportunities for humanity and young people" [20; p. 160]. Therefore, the training of future mathematics teachers places a great responsibility on the teachers of the higher educational institution.

The activity of a teacher of a higher educational institution should be aimed at creating conditions for the formation of the requirements and abilities of a person in the educational process.

A teacher, entering into the educational process based on deep and thorough scientific knowledge of his specialty, must also have excellent knowledge of pedagogical and psychological knowledge, master the teaching methodology and technology.

The following points were expressed in the National Personnel Training Program: "The fact that the majority of teachers, pedagogues and educators are not well trained, their low level of knowledge and profession remains a serious problem, there is a shortage of qualified pedagogues." the extent to which mathematics

teaching methodology is taught in the training of teachers determines the mathematical potential of the future generation [32].

Therefore, in the training of mathematics teachers, the science of mathematics teaching methodology is one of the important and necessary subjects to be studied along with specialized subjects.

Higher education in specialist training (fourth year of education) is focused on creative professional activity, appropriate mathematical culture that allows for the formation of a creatively thinking person, and ensuring a sufficiently high mathematical training of specialists. As noted in the regulatory and legal documents of higher education, this stage consists of training specialists with methodical training in independent creative profession.

The subject "Methodology of teaching mathematics" includes the following topics: Methodology of teaching mathematics as a subject, the content of the mathematics course, methods of teaching mathematics, the use of interactive methods in organizing mathematics teaching, forms of organizing mathematics teaching .

Currently, the requirements of the State educational standard, new concepts of education, improvement of quality and efficiency, etc., require serious changes in the methodical-mathematical training of students to work with their students during the internship period.

The training of mathematics teachers also requires serious changes in connection with the tendency to develop a creative personality in students in general secondary and professional educational institutions in the process of teaching mathematics and mathematics teaching methods. In recent years, certain works have been carried out in this direction.

We will describe the existing research on the issue of methodical-mathematical training of future mathematics teachers. We begin by looking at some of the research on our area of interest in secondary school mathematics teacher training. In our opinion, it is appropriate to dwell in detail on the research work dedicated to the methodical-mathematical training of future mathematics teachers. Improving the methodological training of future mathematics teachers in the field of pedagogy in higher educational institutions in the field of mathematics and its teaching methodology corresponds to the research direction we have chosen. It allows the future teachers of mathematics to work as mature specialists who have a perfect knowledge of the methodology of teaching "Mathematics", which is considered the main subject in the curriculum of their specialty, and who can use innovative technologies.

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